

THE USE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY (ICT) IN TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN INDIA

G. Immanuel¹, B. Sridevi^{2*}, P. Bindu³, G. Sankar⁴ and P. Anusooya⁵

¹ Assistant Professor (Senior Grade), Department of English, Saveetha Engineering College, Thandalam, Chennai. Email: immanuelg@saveetha.ac.in, immanuelganesan93@gmail.com,
ORCID ID: orcid.org/0000-0002-1415-4735

² Assistant Professor, Department of English, Saveetha Engineering College, Thandalam, Chennai.

*Corresponding Author Email: sridevib@saveetha.ac.in, bhas.sridevi@gmail.com,
ORCID ID: orcid.org/0009-0007-5020-2646

³ Assistant Professor, Department of English, Rajalakshmi Institute of Technology, Chembarambakkam, Chennai. Email: bindu.p@ritchennai.edu.in,
ORCID ID: orcid.org/0009-0000-3245-8727

⁴ Assistant Professor, Department of English, Vellore Institute of Technology, Vellore. Email: sankarliterature@gmail.com, ORCID ID: orcid.org/0000-0002-2464-3727

⁵ Assistant Professor, Department of English, National College, (Autonomous), Affiliated to Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli. Email: anusooya87@gmail.com

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.12896294](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12896294)

Abstract

ICT plays a crucial role in English language learning in India, as it is widely recognized as a necessary tool in today's learning environment. This is due to its significant impact on advancing knowledge in language learning. As the globe becomes more connected, it's crucial to employ technology to enhance language acquisition. This research explores the role of ICT in language acquisition and identifies potential benefits for optimal performance. Some of the concerns include no internet access. Technology has become an integral part of our ever-changing world. Previously students begin to walk what they see and use technology around them. In schools and colleges, they begin using technology to increase their understanding of content standards. Usage of computers, tablets, and the software associated with these devices, become a tool for both teachers and students to increase their mastery of the standards exclusively through one umbrella-term, technology. Language learning is well developed through this methodology. As technology becomes more accessible, there is a greater desire for its use in the classroom. With the increasing relevance of technology in schools since the early twenty-first century, it may be time to begin employing technological wavier in education, which provides a fantastic approach for students to learn new knowledge. Teachers are starting to use technology in their classrooms to help students comprehend many of the curriculum areas. The purpose of this article is to discuss the influence and efficiency of technology-based English language learning, as well as the increase in cognitive levels.

Keywords: Technology, Language Learning, Tertiary Level Learners, Global Citizens.

INTRODUCTION

The usage of technology has a significant impact on pupils as they become global citizens. The need for technology teaching and integration in schools is growing rapidly. Many reviews highlighted important areas of technology that have a substantial impact on kids' achievement and cognitive development. Students who have access to computers and technology in their education have a greater accomplishment rate and grade point average than those who have little or no access to technological learning. Instructors must also have a thorough understanding of the technology in order to successfully assist their pupils through its use.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Many quantitative studies include pre- and post-tests to ensure successful results. They undoubtedly have a favorable impact on perception in the teaching and learning processes. English language is a content area that can be delivered in a variety of ways rather than taught. It is a subject that receives mixed support, yet pupils appreciate and comprehend it. As a result, their affective domain levels increase. Much of this can be attributable to the manner in which the subject is delivered or taught. As technology becomes more prevalent in classrooms, teachers will be able to use it as an additional way of instruction, particularly for language training. There have been other similar research conducted in this sector. This study investigates how computer-based instruction influences student achievement and attitudes towards instruction.

A majority of educational institutions followed traditional mode of teaching invariably but a majority of professors of the reputable private educational institution of Technology from which two authors of this paper hail, opted for online teaching using BigBlueButton ,Open Source Web Conferencing for a few courses and Moodle, open-source Learning Platform for every course and the first author of this paper had an experience of teaching employing BigBlueButton a few semesters ago long before the pandemic period.

Online teaching is the need of the hour to avert any spread of infection. This drastic change caught teachers and students unaware. How many of them braced to follow online teaching? Has the stage been set well for online teaching and how many teachers received adequate training? Are they well-equipped to handle online classes?

Does the prior exposure help the private institution to make a smooth transition?

Statement of the problem:

Many quantitative studies include pre- and post-tests to ensure successful results. They undoubtedly have a favorable impact on perception in the teaching and learning processes. English language is a content area that can be delivered in a variety of ways rather than taught. It is a subject that receives mixed support, yet pupils appreciate and comprehend it. As a result, their affective domain levels increase. Much of this can be attributed. The availability of necessary gadgets and internet access is the million-dollar question. The main obstacles that users experience include internet access, the availability of devices, administrators' concerns about these issues, and problems that students and teachers have with online technologies.

Relational Study reviews:

1. Technological Problems: Internet connectivity encounters a lot of impediments to reach users. Students in the remote area, even within the city during the natural calamities meet challenges in receiving uninterrupted connectivity. The interruptions in connectivity play the spoil sport game especially during the conduct of exam online. This interruption leads to student's and teacher's loss of time in the re-conduct of tests/examinations and thus to frustration later. Muthuprasada's survey research in 2021 on agriculture university graduates with structured & unstructured questionnaires shows students' rating on a 5 point scale after being calculated the percentage and being tried with "a measure of consensus for each

statement" ensuring the constraints due to data limit, data speed rated as the major hindrance to online learning.

2. Gadgets are expensive and affordability to devices demands attention on the part of administrators. Not only the lack of stock or/and malfunctioning gadgets but also the lack of technical know how to operate those gadgets either by the teacher or/and the student check them from using for online teaching.
3. Platforms for streaming are umpteen but the need arises for confirming whether it caters to the needs of students from different area of the world and suitable for teachers to handle classes without any intrusion of outsiders. Each has its own advantages and disadvantages but careful attention to ensure whether it allows others to peep in will help teachers to be aware of the presence of strangers on the platform of their choice. At least a few teachers' limited expertise in handling such platforms also poses a problem for online teaching (Noor 2020).
4. Managerial Problems: The concerns of administrators on teaching online receive much attention before simply forcing others to adopt online teaching is a must. The decision to adopt online teaching will perhaps be ineffective and yet no preparedness and proper understanding of its implications deters the successful implementation and realization of its worth. Essuman(2015) revealed through his study the lack of proper technical support, motivation and understanding about the over workload involved in the process. Hodges(2020) confirmed in his study the need for considering all the possibilities for effective online teaching before transition. Instructional design as well as planning carries much weight as learning is cognitive and social. Since temporary shift compromises on quality, the institution should consider skill training and accessibility, needs and attributes of all the students registered to ensure quality teaching and learning. He highlighted the futility of media comparison study since it fails to emphasis the quality improvement in comparison. The lack of technology management and support systems can be a cause of worry in this rapid transition in a few institutions (Noor 2020).

The ill-timing of Instructional time and space happens as a result of adopting blending method of teaching to suit the needs of students and the course content. The real challenge will be to "develop fluency with teaching and learning with technology, not just with technology itself" (p.44 as cited in Bair 2011). Setting the parameters clearly should be the main concerns of any institutional management.

5. Above all, conduct of exams as well as evaluation offline is relatively convenient for institution to follow. The option of online teaching questions the reliability of online assessment and evaluation. The reliability carries a lot of weight in the conduct of online tests/exams. Milone(2017) drives home the point the online proctoring service, ProctorU's high technological and additional monetary demand on students is more than benefits from its assurance of integrity. So, the difficulty in preventing students from cheating in exams is inevitable (Kumar 2021) due to such prohibitive cost of proctoring service.
6. Pedagogical Problems: Online teaching has both merits and demerits like face -to -face teaching. Even though no mode of teaching is perfect, yet the assurance of the presence of students the other end creates a lot of issues and even if their presence is for the attendance, their attentiveness is poor in some cases. The real time teaching is possible but sincere learning is a question. The assuaging of students for their cerebral needs is beyond our reach sometime because of their

expectations are more and their access to information has immediacy and so, this becomes, sometimes, intimidating to teachers.

Impact on technology and globalization

With the advent of technology and globalization, 21st century has become the era of bilingualism or multilingualism. A survey suggests that from year 2000, English speaking and learning has become a necessity. And in 14 years after 2000 graphs of English speakers and learners is increasing day by day. Recently I got a chance to visit Oxford university for a summer seminar, and was really astonished to know that many countries like ours one facing problems in L2 learning. They have pronunciation problems, grammatical errors and construction problems too. But many countries are using modern gadgets and are technologically advanced. They made a fusion of English teaching with technology and electronic aid. They are progressing and finding good results. There we have been introduced with many devices, apps and soft wares which are really helpful for English teaching. English is spoken as L2 in many countries but use of technical aids has made teaching easier, apt and accessible.

The Use of ICT in English Teaching • To increase students' interest in teaching, ICT and multimedia are required. There are numerous apps, devices, and their uses that entice pupils to learn. • Traditional teaching has traditionally made it difficult for pupils to interact with one another. As a result, they become passive listeners. They are unable to form sentences or talk because they lack an understanding of language structure, meaning, and comprehension. Technological advancements allow people to see visual and acoustic aids, which improves communication skills. • The use of ICT and multimedia enhances students' understanding and provides them with opportunities in classroom study. • Multimedia enriches instructional content, and there are numerous apps that allow teachers to communicate with students one-on-one at any time, even when they are not physically there. • Technology.

Development of technology in a new world

“Education technology improves students' attitudes towards technology and learning, because it can customize the learning experience to the student and it makes learning more enjoyable, and interactive (Valdez and Hutchinson 34). Information about student test results based on their pre- and post-assessments will be provided by the quantitative technique. An approach to quantitative research is used in this type of investigation. It offers more succinct information that clearly illustrates the relationship between student accomplishments for both focus groups and how their opinions have evolved over time by employing a quantitative method research technique. Numerous researches attest to the beneficial effects of technology on students' perceptions. According to the study, a variety of factors influence how technology affects students' academic performance. To start, technology needs to be utilized in a way that helps teachers with the material they are already teaching. That is, rather of serving as the primary source of education, it serves as a secondary source.

Another study found that “students who use technology were (a) spending more time involved in collaborative work, (b) participating in more project-based instruction, (c) producing writing of higher quality and greater length, (d) gaining increased access to information, (e) improving research analysis skills, and (f) spending more time doing homework digitally. Studies have also determined that using technology at the beginning of class sessions helped students stay on task and concentrate.” (Devlin 2013).

METHODS AND DESIGN

Studies with quantitative research methods opine, “Quantitative research generally reduces measurement to numbers. In survey research, for example, attitudes are usually measured by using rating scales.” (Johnson & Christensen 37). By using a quantitative method research approach it provided a dimension that offered to show if there is a correlation between both focus groups, while also understanding what is occurring from the participants’ point of view. The quantitative method provides specific data relating to student tests scores based on pre- and post-assessments. The quantitative method also uses surveys provided to all participants to show changes in attitudes towards the use of technology throughout the study.

The study’s objective was to ascertain whether or not adopting computer-based instruction only for language learning and cognitive development has an effect on students’ attitudes and achievement. Students will be randomly assigned to one of two groups—the experimental group or the controlled group—as participants in these investigations. The identical material is being presented to each group, but using two different delivery modalities. Students in both teaching groups will have their increased understanding assessed using the pre- and post-test data. To ascertain the overall growth produced by all students, the data will be gathered. Then data will be analyzed to determine which instructional group, teacher-led or computer-based, achieved a greater increase in achievement on the post-test.

Through data collection and analysis, it will be comprehended that students taught through teacher-led instruction had an overall higher average passing score than students receiving only computer-based instruction. Student attitudes towards technology will also an important factor when deciding how impactful technology implementation is to academic achievement. These findings provide educators with enough data to determine that computer-based instruction can be used for academic growth in students; however it is not as convincing as teacher-led instruction.

Hence such kind of studies explores how computer-based instruction affects student achievement and their attitudes toward instruction. These researches provide valuable insights into the importance of technology use in the classroom. As society continues to use technology on a daily basis, students need to have more opportunities to learn through technology in the classroom. This however, does not mean students should be using computers as the only means of instruction in the classroom.

The use of computers and technology for primary instruction did improve student attitudes towards learning and many students feel the learning was much more enjoyable when using computers than learning from the teacher. Hence it is worth-proving to believe that all computer-based instruction programs are beneficial, but that using technology and computer-based instruction as a secondary source of instruction can be beneficial for students’ overall academic achievement, improve the level of cognitive domain and improve student attitudes towards technology and learning as well.

CONCLUSION

There are several drawbacks to computer-based learning and technology integration in addition to its many benefits. One issue that should not be disregarded is the cost of technology. The expense of technology can make many institutions reconsider making acquisitions, given the current state of education financing shortages. The

additional expenses for technology integration—which many people ignore—were mentioned in an article comparing computers and texts in classrooms. “It is important to remember that maintaining school systems comes with additional costs, such as those associated with maintaining computer systems, guarding against equipment theft, and supporting teacher staff development.” Wishengrad, R 4. Technology can also prevent kids from having critical in-person contacts that are essential for human development. Even so, this evolution offers a better chance of success in terms of English language learning pedagogy as well.

Works cited

- 1) Arifah, A. (2014). Study on the use of technology in ELT classroom: Teachers' perspective (M.A. Thesis). Department of English and Humanities, BRAC University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
- 2) Aydin, S. (2013). Teachers' perceptions about the use of computers in EFL teaching and learning: The case of Turkey. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 26(3), 214-233. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2012.654495>
- 3) Baytak, A., Tarman, B., & Ayas, C. (2011). Experiencing technology integration in education: Children's perceptions. *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, 3(2), 139-151. Retrieved June 17, 2018, from <https://www.iejee.com/index.php/IEJEE/article/view/233>
- 4) Beatty, K. (2003). *Teaching and Researching Computer Assisted Language Learning*. New York: Longman.
- 5) Becker, H. J. (2000). Findings from the teaching, learning, and computing survey: Is Larry Cuban right? *Education Policy Analysis Archives*, 8(51). <https://doi.org/10.14507/epaa.v8n51.2000> Beijing foreign Language Teaching and Research Press. (n.d.). Retrieved from <http://www.onestopenglish.cll>
- 6) Brown, H. D. (2001). *Teaching by principles. An interactive approach to language pedagogy* Beijing foreign Language Teaching and Research Press. www.onestopenglish.com
- 7) Devlin, T. J., Feldhaus, C. R., & Bentrem, K. M. (2013). The Evolving classroom: A Study of Traditional and Technology-Based Instruction in a STEM Classroom”, *Journal of Technology Education*. 25(1), Oct 2106.
- 8) Johnson & Christensen, (2008). *Educational Research: Quantitative, Qualitative, and Mixed Approaches*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, Inc.
- 9) Lesley Harbon & Ruth Fielding (2022) Continuity of Language Learning from Primary to Secondary: Secondary School Language Learners' Investment and Identity Development in Language Learning, *Journal of Language, Identity & Education*, DOI: 10.1080/15348458.2022.2092739
- 10) Valdez and Hutchinson (2006). “Tracking Long-Term Effects of Technology-Based Education on Former at Risk-Continuation High School Students”. Web Nov 11 2017 <http://hdl.handle.net/10211.3/122035>
- 11) Reena Mitta, (2015). Use of Technology in English Language Teaching: Is it Helping Students and Teachers?, *The International Academic Forum*.
- 12) Wishengrad, R. (1999). *Are Paper Textbooks Ready to Fold?* *Education Digest*. 64(6), 57. <https://search.ebscohost.com/>